
Awareness, Understanding, and Acceptance of CEAT Students of ISU-I Towards its Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives

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ABSTRACT: The study focused in determining the Awareness, Understanding and Acceptance of the CEAT Students of ISU-I towards the Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives. A descriptive survey research was employed in this study and purposive sampling was used to determine the number of respondents from the college (CEAT). Statistical Mean was used to determine , analyse and assess the awareness, acceptance and understanding of the ISU -VMGO. Questionnaire was patterned from a survey instrument used from similar studies conducted within the university. The study reveals that the CEAT Students are highly aware of the Vision and Mission of Isabela State University (ISU) and to the Objectives of their respective curricular programs. With regard to the dissemination of the VMGO the respondents are generally aware that the VMGO are displayed in bulletin boards ; printed in catalogs, manuals and other materials; broadcasted in media and/or internet/website; and widely disseminated to the different agencies, institutions, industry sectors and the community as a whole. Moreover, they greatly accept and understand the Vision, Mission and the Objectives of the program where they belong and the responsibility of realizing such objectives in their own capacity. Widest dissemination of the VMGO through various forms of communication through media/internet and other related activities should be one of the concern of the Institution to further strengthen support from stakeholders.

KEYWORDS: Vision, Mission, Goals, Objectives, Awareness, Acceptance, Understanding

INTRODUCTION

The vision, mission, goals and objectives (VMGO) serve as guidelines of all the university's operations. However, VMGO is not included in the computation of the mean for the areas evaluated as set by the AACCCUP. Moreover, VMGO is the most fundamental of all the (10) ten areas to be surveyed in AACCCUP Accreditation. It is essential that an institution formulates a vision and mission which serve as the bases of all activities and educational development. Everything in the university is justified only to the extent that it realizes its vision and mission. A vision is an statement about what the organization wants to become and therefore resonate with all the members of the institution and help them have the sense of ownership and become part of the entire organization. It provides the impression, character and direction of its operation.

Accrediting Agency for Chartered Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACCCUP) possessed certain standard of quality excellence based on the institutional operations in relations to VMGO.

The effectiveness of the VMGO determines its structure, dissemination and acceptability and for this to be attained, the stakeholders of an educational institution have to be aware on its VMGO and fully understand the implication of such.

Feliciano, AC et al.(2012) in their study , "Awareness and Acceptability of the Vision, Mission, Goals and Objectives of Eastern Samar State University" justified that through the proper dissemination, the students, faculty, staff and other stakeholders are informed of the VMGO of the university with high level of acceptance.

The study about the Influence of Strategy Formulation (Vision, Mission and Goals) and Learning on Growth (Fahad AIDhaheri, et al) , results indicated that the strategy implementation (strategy, structure and human resources) has significant and positive impact on organizational performance but significant effect on learning and growth.

The findings on the study " Analysis of the mission and vision statements on the strategic plan of Higher Education Institutions (Guven Ozdem, 2011) showed that the theme of "Providing Services for the Education of qualified Workforce was frequently used in mission statement, while "services concerning the research function" was frequently used in vision statement.

The study "The Role of Vision and Mission in the Organization Development Practices"(Xavier, Vincent 2014) findings showed that most of the respondents accepted the vision and mission of the organization and found out that it is effective function in the overall Development process.

The effectiveness of the VMGO lies in its structure and dissemination. The students and other stakeholders must have full awareness , understanding and acceptance of the VMGO as a measure of its proper dissemination.

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Isabela State University is guided by its new vision, mission, goals and objectives as it continues to achieve academic excellence and produce quality graduates. Its vision is “The Isabela State University as a leading, vibrant, comprehensive and research university in the country and the ASEAN region”. Its mission is committed to develop highly trained and globally competent professionals; generate innovative and cuttingedge knowledge and technologies for people empowerment and sustainable development; engage in viable resource generation programs; and maintain and enhance stronger partnership under good governance to advance the interests of national and international communities.

Since ISU’s new VMGO was newly approved (2019) , the researchers deemed it wise to conduct a study regarding the awareness, understanding and acceptance by the students in the College of Engineering, Architecture and Technology at the City of Ilagan Campus.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This survey sought to determine the awareness, understanding and acceptance of the Students of the College of Engineering, Architecture and Technology of Isabela State University, City of Ilagan Campus towards its vision, mission, goals and objective Specifically it aimed to:

1. Determine the awareness of CEAT students with regard to the Vision and Mission of ISU, the Goals of the College and Objectives of the curricular programs offered.(VMGO).
2. Determine the awareness of CEAT students with regard to the dissemination of the Vision and Mission of ISU, the Goals of the College and Objectives of the curricular programs offered.(VMGO).
3. Determine the acceptance and understanding of the CEAT students with regard to the vision and Mission of ISU, the Goals of the College and Objectives of the curricular programs offered.(VMGO).

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey research was employed in this study to determine the awareness, understanding and acceptability of the students from the College of Engineering, Architecture, Industrial and Information Technology. The questionnaire was patterned from a survey instrument used from similar studies conducted within the university.

A purposive sampling was used to determine the number of respondents (200) from the college (CEAT). The respondents are the students from the different programs in the college: BS Civil and Electrical Engineering (CE), BS Architecture (AR), BS Industrial Technology (Indus-Tech) and BS Information Technology (IT).

Statistical Mean was used to determine , analyse and assess the awareness, acceptance and understanding of the Vision, Mission of ISU, the Goals and Objectives of the curricular programs offered.

The following scale and interpretation were used to better understand the quantitative data.

	Response	
Mean		
1) 1.00 -1.49	Highly Aware	Greatly Accept/understand
2) 1.50 -2.49	Aware	Accept/Understand
3) 2.50 - 3.49	least Aware	Slightly Accept/Understand
4) 3.50 - 4.00	Not Aware	Not Accept/Understand

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1. Awareness of the CEAT Students on the VMGO

Statements	Mean					Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	CE (n=30)	EE (n=20)	AR (n=19)	IT (n=31)	Indus - Tech (n=100)		
I am aware of the Vision of ISU	3.33	3.45	3.79	3.548	3.75	3.57	Highly Aware
I am aware of the Mission of ISU	3.33	3.25	3.58	3.645	3.75	3.51	Highly Aware

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I am aware of the Goals of College	2.97	3.65	3.37	3.226	3.7	3.38	Aware
I am aware of the Objectives of the program offered	3.6	3.55	3.79	3.581	3.74	3.65	Highly Aware
Overall	3.31	3.475	3.63	3.5	3.74	3.53	Highly Aware

Legend: CE- Civil Engineering, EE - Electrical Engineering, AR Architecture IT-Information Technology , Indus-Tech- Industrial
 The data in Table 1 shows that the CEAT Students are “Highly Aware” of the Vision and Mission of Isabela State University (ISU) and to the Objectives of their respective curricular programs. In general, the respondents are “Highly Aware”(wm =3.53) on the Vision and Mission of ISU , while the lowest mean (wm = 3.38) on the goals of the of the college. The school vision, mission and goals are very important part of the curriculum development in as much as it serves as the guiding post around which all educated efforts, including the curriculum should be aligned,(Cacho, C. et al, 2019)

Table 2. Awareness of the CEAT Students on the Dissemination of the VMGO

Statements	Mean					Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	CE (n=30)	EE (n=20)	AR (n=19)	IT (n=31)	Indus - Tech (n=100)		
I am aware that the VMGO are displayed in bulletin boards.	3.33	3.75	3.79	3.9	3.75	3.71	Highly Aware
I am aware that the VMGO are printed in catalogs, manuals and other materials	2.83	3.25	3.37	3.55	3.7	3.34	Aware
I am aware that the VMGO are broadcasted in media and/or internet/website	2.83	3.4	3.26	2.87	3.3	3.13	Aware
I am aware that the VMGO are widely disseminated to the different agencies, institutions, industry sectors and the community as a whole	2.87	3.05	3.47	2.81	3.17	3.07	Aware
Overall	2.97	3.36	3.47	3.28	3.48	3.31	Aware

Legend: CE- Civil Engineering, EE - Electrical Engineering, AR - Architecture IT- Information Technology , Indus-Tech- Industrial
 Table 2 shows that the CEAT Students are generally “ aware” (wm = 3.31) that the VMGO are displayed in bulletin boards ; printed in catalogs, manuals and other materials; broadcasted in media and/or internet/website; and widely disseminated to the different agencies, institutions, industry sectors and the community as a whole.

However, the respondents expressed that they are

“highly aware” that the VMGO are displayed in bulletin boards, with highest weighted mean (wm=3.71) and the lowest mean (wm=3.07) is from the awareness that the VMGO are widely disseminated to the different agencies, institutions, industry sectors and the community as a whole.

Table 3. Acceptance and Understanding of the CEAT Students to the VMGO

Statements	Mean					Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	CE (n=30)	EE (n=20)	AR (n=19)	IT (n=31)	IndusTech (n=100)		
I accept and understand the Vision of ISU	3.13	3.75	3.79	3.65	3.8	3.62	Greatly Accept and Understand

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I accept and understand the Mission of ISU	3.23	3.75	3.79	3.65	3.85	3.65	Greatly Accept and Understand
I accept and understand the Goals of College	3.07	3.4	3.37	3.29	3.7	3.37	Accept and Understand
I accept and understand the Objectives of the program where I belong and the responsibility of realizing such objectives in my own capacity.	3.5	4	4	3.9	3.98	3.88	Greatly Accept and Understand
Overall	3.23	3.73	3.74	3.62	3.83	3.63	Greatly Accept and Understand

Legend: CE- Civil Engineering, EE - Electrical Engineering, AR - Architecture ITInformation Technology , Indus-Tech- Industrial
 Table 3 shows that the CEAT Students in general “Greatly Accept and Understand” the Vision, Mission and the Objectives of the program where they belong and the responsibility of realizing such objectives in their own capacity. Meanwhile, the respondents “Accept and Understand” the goals of the College where their programs are associated.

CONCLUSIONS

On the awareness of the Students regarding the VMGO, they are highly aware of the Vision and Mission of Isabela State University (ISU) and to the Objectives of their respective curricular programs.

On the awareness regarding the dissemination of the VMGO the CEAT Students are generally aware that the VMGO are displayed in bulletin boards ; printed in catalogs, manuals and other materials; broadcasted in media and/or internet/website; and widely disseminated to the different agencies, institutions, industry sectors and the community as a whole. However, the respondents expressed that they are more aware that the VMGO are displayed in bulletin boards and less aware that the VMGO are disseminated to the different agencies, institutions, industry sectors and the community as a whole.

The CEAT Students greatly accept and understand the Vision, Mission and the Objectives of the program where they belong and the responsibility of realizing such objectives in their own capacity.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The Institution should continuously work in raising the awareness of the students regarding the VMGO. Conduct educational activities may be considered to make sure that the students understand such activities are to be undertaken for the realization or attainment of some goals and objectives.

Widest dissemination of the VMGO through various forms of communication through media/internet and other related activities should be one of the concern of the Institution to further strengthen support from stakeholders.

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